

UNIVERSITY OF BRUNEI DARUSSALAM

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HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

INDIVIDUAL ASSIGNMENT 2

CASE STUDY ANALYSIS OF THE AGROWMETRO COMPANY USING THE
HARVARD MODEL

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ABSTRACT

The case study analysis focuses on the Agrowmetro company established in Brunei, which focuses on providing a hydroponics system for the community. The main focus of the analysis will be on the key factor of issues concerning human resource management within the organization. Thus, one of the HRM models, the Harvard model, is applied within the analysis, and from the evaluation, it has proven the usefulness of the model in identifying the major cause of the problem of the challenges faced by the agriculture company. The overview of the analysis, the Agrowmetro company issue is the lack of HR practices implemented within the organization, which causes a lack of human resources and financial scarcity as the main challenges the company faces. The analysis also provides potential solutions that focus on the issues such as employing cost-effective methods on improving their recruitment method, and the ideas on ways to retain employees within the organization. However, there are several important constraints in the application of this particular model, this is because it lacks in providing the solution for the company rather, only aids in identifying the issues.

1. INTRODUCTION

According to Banerjee and Adenaeuer (2014), fundamental changes such as changes in the demand for food supply are predicted to grow in the upcoming 50 years, this is due to the growing numbers of the world population all across the world (as cited by Kalantari et al., 2018). However, the average age of the population of farmers worldwide are currently within the range of high 50s to early 60s years old, therefore, in the modern agriculture market, future generations need to be motivated to increase the global production of food and to solve food security problems (Musa et al., 2020). Kalantari et al. (2018) stated that due to the issue of food supply, there is a need to use more land for agriculture and to accelerate farming activities that will impact global agriculture, which emphasized the value of the use of an efficient technique of cultivation. The Agrowmetro company established by the four Bruneian students is one example of the engagement between the youth and modern agriculture in Brunei Darussalam, and an enterprise itself focuses on modern techniques in growing crops, the use of hydroponics.

1.1. OVERVIEW OF AGROWMETRO COMPANY

In reference to the publication of the *'Inspiring Agripreneurus in Brunei'* book, it provides an overview of the Agrowmetro company. The company mainly specializes in providing and setting up a hydroponics system which is a modern technique in growing and cultivating vegetables. Agrowmetro company has its pipe supplier and all products including hydroponic set complete with pump, pail, total dissolved solution meter, and A and B nutrients, and all these utilities are easy and safe to install. Agrowmetro is a partnership founded and established by four youths who graduated with Higher National Technical Education in Agro-Technology from the IBTE Agro-Technology Campus. As the four entrepreneurs come from families of simple farming roots, they share a deep enthusiasm for agriculture, and due to this same reason,

it has motivated them to start Agrowmetro. In finally deciding to officially start their own company, they decided on the vision and mission of the company which is related to inspire the youths to be involved in agriculture activities and encourage them to pursue their interests in such activities and to develop and transform Brunei's traditional farming into a technological modern way of cultivation in Brunei.

1.2. PROBLEM STATEMENT

The Agrowmetro company also faced several challenges in operating their company. Such challenges include the lack of human resources, which the company experience such hardship due to the lack of capital the company acquired to enable themselves in hiring numbers of labor and providing reasonable payment numbers to operate and develop their company. In attempting to resolve this problem, the entrepreneurs divide their earnings and use any excess finance for the important materials needed such as buying raw materials, pipes, and other tools. The financial scarcity is also one of the main problems the Agrowmetro company suffers as well. The initial finance in the start-up was mainly supported by their teacher, and it was considered as a loan in which they have repaid after successfully sold their first batch of hydroponics sets to their customers.

Another common issue that may arise in operating an agriculture company is the lack of exposure. The first and second problems faced in the Agrowmetro company are interrelated to this stated problem. In understanding that there are very few numbers of people who are aware of the existence of a company in a community who may view or stereotype an agriculture business as unprofitable and unpopular, it can be justified that due to such reason, there are low numbers of potential locals to seek jobs under an agricultural industry. In addition, due to

the lack of awareness of an existing local company that cultivates their own foods, the possibility of locals buying locally grown vegetables and fruits is low, which leads them to potentially buying the imported ones instead. Thus, affect the company's sales to reduce their financial scarcity and hire a potential workforce to overcome their hardship in recruiting human resources.

2. THEORY-DRIVEN ANALYSIS

The challenges mentioned which are currently experienced by the entrepreneurs are viewed as the common and foreseeable problems within an agricultural company in Brunei. However, a Human Resource Management (HRM) model can be a tool to expand the view in identifying and critically analyzing the main factor in which causes such problems the Agrowmetro faces. Human resource management models are based on the theoretical framework and practices to improve the process of managing human resources within an organization. According to Cakar (2003), with regards to the HRM models and the business process, the model is applied to recognize and identify some gaps which caused some issues to arise. As there are various types of the existing human resource management model, the Harvard Model is considered as one of those models, and the model will be discussed and applied to expand the analysis in the main factors of issues within the Agrowmetro company.

The Harvard Model

The Harvard Model is the earliest example of a soft HRM model to be developed. Beer et al (1984) theorizes the model at Harvard University and recognizes the validity and existence of the organization's multiple stakeholders (as cited by Gado, 2018). The figure below portrays the framework of the Harvard model for human resource management.

Figure 1

Figure 1 shows the six components included in the Harvard model. Namely, the Stakeholder Interest, Situational Factors, HRM policies, HRM outcomes, and Long-term Consequences. The components in the model may be viewed into two parts which are, the human resource system which represents labor relations and personnel administration perspectives such as employee influence, human resource flow, rewards, and work systems, whereas the second part is the HRM territory, which shows how HRM is closely connected with both the external environment and the internal organization (Cakar, 2003).

a. Stakeholders' Interests and Situational Factors

Stakeholders' interests recognize the importance of the compromising interests of different parties. The internal and external environment factors of organizations serve as major constraints to the development of HRM policies. While Situational factors recognize the internal and external business environmental factors and these factors act as major constraints to the development of HRM in addition to the factors of the stakeholders' interests. In the Agrowmetro company, there was no clear definition of the existence of the establishment of an HR department. Based on the available information given, the company mentioned only have the four entrepreneurs act as the laborer in the company. Thus, the availability of a certain HR department is not clearly defined, which may lead to the idea of the company to have not to implement efficient and effective HR practices within the company.

b. HRM Policies

The HRM policies chosen are influenced by the Situational Factors, and Stakeholders' Interest, these include the core HR activities, like recruitment, training, and reward systems. Gado (2018) has defined each HR policy areas, firstly, the HR flows are the motion or flow which concerns managing the flow of people into, and out of the organization, this includes decisions on recruitment and selection, promotion, termination of employment, and related issues of job security, career development, advancement, and fair treatment. Secondly, the reward system is the regulation on how employees are rewarded for their work which can be tangible and intangible, the main significant point is that the employees need to be motivated, rewarded for their work, and besides, the work system or payment system should be designed for the benefits of the employees as well. Thirdly, employee influence means that the employees can become

a part of the organization as a family by the delegation of work or task and responsibility. Lastly, the work system is the working design and employee alignment in which the design itself makes the work in the organization to work effectively and efficiently.

In the case of the Agrowmetro company, due to the factor that has been identified above in regards to the absence of the HR department that lead to the unclear HR practices that have been done within the company, the HR policies will greatly be affected. Firstly, due to the lack of basic HR practices, this may be one of the reasons behind the cause of the lack of human resources that the company is facing. The practices on recruitment and selection of potential employees are low due to the insufficient HR practices used in recruiting, selecting, or promoting job vacancies within the company. Secondly, another HR policy area that can be identified concerning the company's problem is the reward system. As mentioned previously, the company suffers financial scarcity which also affects their ability to hire new workers and provide financial payment, thus leads to the inability to hire employees. This may be justified due to the poorly designed payment or reward system within the company.

c. HRM Outcomes

Results will be positive when the HRM policies are done well, while negative results are resulted due to the weak HRM practices applied within the organization. Gado (2018) stated that when making HRM decisions on policies, management should consider the HR policy the four C's which are commitment, congruence, competence, and cost-effectiveness. Firstly, in the emphasis of the commitment factor, as the four youths share the same interests and passions in pursuing the agricultural industry, the commitment force of the entrepreneurs exists.

Meanwhile, as the four entrepreneurs are new to the business and they are all graduates from the same field in the Agro-Technology course, the skills and knowledge of HRM within the company are low and thus may justify the lack of competence in the application of HR policies.

d. Long-term Consequences

This can be achieved by ensuring that the HRM outcomes are positive. These can be individual, organizational, and societal consequences. Beer et al., (1984) proposed that long-term consequences can be measured by evaluating the four C's, and through this, there will be increased productivity, organizational effectiveness which will influence the shareholder's interest and situational factor hence making it a cycle (Gado, 2018). In the application of the HR flow system within the framework, it can be said that the Agrowmetro company will not be able to operate effectively and efficiently in the long-term.

Key Problems

From the analysis of the company's business process and management with the implication of the Harvard model of HRM. The main problem within the company is the lack of HR practices, in regard to the management's skills and abilities to conduct sufficient HR policies within the company to prepare themselves in recruiting, selecting, and giving rewards to the employees efficiently. The low number of human resources itself is interrelated to the financial availability within the company, as the company is unable to sufficiently acquired adequate numbers of workers, they were unable to create and possibly meet the demand of their potential clients to successfully achieve good numbers of sales.

3. ALTERNATIVE SOLUTION

As the company suffers the lack of human resources, the use of social media to raise awareness on the availability of job vacancies can be applied and the advantage of using social media is the ability to broaden the scope of the audience who are potential in the agricultural work at a cheap price. However, as social media is accessible by anyone, several competitors will also promote their job vacancies on the same platform, and this will not justifiably assure that the Agrowmetro company to easily acquire and attract potential employees.

In the emphasize of the reward system of the company, Truss (1997) stated that the Harvard model typically viewed as the soft version of HRM, which means the human relations movement, and the utilization of individual talents and McGregor's Theory Y perspective on individuals who are high of commitment at work, and rather to be self-regulated than being controlled. This also highlights that the employees are assumed to be motivated by appraisal, recognition, and delegation of the task instead of by payment. Thus, the application of providing other reward benefits may effectively be applied for the employees.

Other than that, the Agrowmetro company should provide sufficient HR practices by also cutting the cost in overcoming their problems. After they can employ numbers of workers, giving a direct one-to-one training from the management team may be effective as it improves the worker's skills and abilities at lower costs, and in addition, this will promote the feeling of belonging towards the employees as the training itself may improve employer and employees relationship. Another benefit is that the employees will be motivated in performing their tasks. However, as there are

still numbers of companies that offer alternative jobs rather than the agricultural focus of the industry, the possibility of the workers changing jobs is endless.

To overcome the potential disadvantage to the solutions, the Agrowmetro company may promote their company by creating attractive posters or advertisement of the Agrowmetro company at a low cost. The development of technologies proved that anyone could access and experience new knowledge and skills via the internet, thus, can aid the management team in creating innovative designs, posters, or ads to attract job seekers. This can resolve the issue of the lack of exposure to the agricultural industry or the company itself, as most youths are accessible via the internet. In addition, will potentially develop the youths' interest in working under the agricultural industries in Brunei.

4. CONCLUSION

From the analysis of the Agrowmetro company with the application of the Harvard model of HRM, it is proven that the model itself able to identify the key factor of the main issues within the company. From the model itself, in identifying the company's factor of issues, each area of the framework is viewed in the context of the company. From the overall evaluation of the Agrowmetro company in the use of the HRM model, the overview of the main issue is due to the lack of HR practices implemented within the organization in which it can be said as the root of the main issues the company is facing. Therefore, in overcoming the issues, the company should promote their job vacancies efficiently in regards to the cost-effective and the attraction of potential employees, such as via social media. In addition to that, the promoting of vacancies will gather potential workers who could be able to help and improve the business performance, thus, increase the chances of sales development, which would solve the financial scarcity issue.

5. RECOMMENDATIONS

Although the Harvard model may be utilized in identifying the major roots of the business's main problems, it does not specifically aid the Agrowmetro company in resolving the issues. The company may only identify the problem in the context of assuming the workers are to be treated as soft HRM. In that sense, it is not justifiable to assume that all the potential workers the company may employ, fit into the view as a Theory Y of workers from McGregor's theory of the employees. Thus, could not officially comprehend this one model as the company should observe other HRM model as well.

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